

UCD SCHOOL OF ARCHAEOLOGY

ARCH41390 Masters Dissertation Syllabus

Module Coordinator

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With contributions from

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MODULE OUTLINE

During this module you will develop your own independent master's dissertation research project, progressing through key stages of research design, including identifying a clear research question, selecting an appropriate dataset and methodology, and drafting a proposal. We will address topics that are foundational for conducting academic research, including constructing research questions, developing strategies for time management, identifying and planning for potential obstacles, understanding research ethics, and summarising your work in a presentation to an academic audience. The module structure will incorporate lectures, small group discussion, and interactive activities. Spring Trimester assignments are designed to scaffold the process of research design, including the development of a project abstract, presentation, and proposal, with final proposals approved by the School of Archaeology in time to allow students to work on their projects in Summer Trimester. The overall aim of the two-trimester module is to provide the research skills necessary to design and develop your master's dissertation, which will be submitted during the summer trimester.

LEARNING OUTCOMES

Upon completing this module, you will have:

- 1) Learned how to identify and develop an academic research question
- 2) Designed and conducted an independent research project
- 3) Learned to prepare for and overcome the challenges inherent in carrying out research
- 4) Produced a 15,000-word dissertation (the thesis)

SCHOOL OF ARCHAEOLOGY CULTURE

UCD School of Archaeology is committed to creating an environment where diversity is celebrated and everyone is treated fairly, regardless of gender, age, race, disability, ethnic origin, religion, sexual orientation, civil status, family status or membership of the travelling community. The School is also committed to the promotion of a study environment that upholds the dignity and respect of the individual and that supports every individual's right to study in an environment free of any form of harassment, intimidation or bullying. For further information and supports, please visit <http://www.ucd.ie/archaeology/edi>

ASSESSMENT AND FORMAL SUBMISSION OF YOUR MINOR THESIS

The thesis will be approximately 15,000 words in length. Please note that the bibliography is not included in word count. I recommend that you familiarize yourself with the School of Archaeology [policy on word counts](#) (including the 20% leeway)

This is a substantial 30-credit module comprising the second and third trimester of your MSc programme. Accordingly, it is worth three times as much as any other module in your master's programme.

1. You will submit your MSc thesis as a single PDF document complete on the ARCH41390 Masters Dissertation Brightspace site. The submission deadline is Thursday, 8th August, 2024, no later than 3:00 pm.
2. You are also expected to submit one hard copy, conforming to UCD standards as outlined in the [UCD Guidelines for Preparation, Submission, Examination and Dissemination of Research Degree Theses](#) (black binding, gold lettering), which will be held in the School of Archaeology archive. This hard copy should be submitted to the UCD School of Archaeology office before Thursday, 15th August, 2024, no later than 3:00 pm.

If you intend to submit your thesis earlier than these deadlines, you should make formal arrangements with the School office (masters.archaeology@ucd.ie), recognising that staff may be away on leave in July and August.

If you have questions about dissertation style, presentation, formatting, layout and content information or other issues, please liaise with your academic supervisor before having your thesis bound.

There is a UCD policy on dissertations and theses, so please do refer to the [UCD Policy on Theses in Graduate Taught Programmes](#) on presentation and formatting.

While the above date is the submission deadline, you should of course be expecting to submit drafts of your chapters to your supervisor for comment as you progress. This is common academic practice—submission of a thesis without the oversight of your supervisor would be seen as highly unusual and potentially problematic.

For students who cannot make the final published submission deadline, please first discuss this issue with your supervisor. Then, carefully read the [UCD Policy on Extenuating Circumstances](#) prior to submitting a formal [Extenuating Circumstances application](#) online via SISweb. If you do make a formal extenuating circumstances application, be sure to inform your supervisor and Jess in her capacity as the module MC.

SCHOOL SUBMISSION PROCEDURE

You are expected to submit two copies of your minor thesis: (1) a bound hard copy; (2) a pdf digital submission.

Hard Copy

The hard copy of your minor thesis should be submitted to the School Office (K013) no later than the published deadline. This copy must be black and hard-bound with gold lettering on the cover which will remain in the School's permanent thesis collection. Examples of hard-bound thesis are available in the School Office (K013) should you wish to see an example. A copy of the Graduate Minor Thesis Submission Form must be submitted as a separate document when presenting your thesis for formal submission. The submission form can be found in the [UCD Policy on Theses in Graduate Taught Programmes](#).

Students have traditionally used [The Thesis Centre](#) on Camden Street to arrange to have one copy hard bound (in black with gold lettering); however other companies that can be found online offer a similar service such as Reads Printing (www.reads.ie).

Digital Submission

You are also required to submit a pdf version of your minor thesis online at Brightspace (i.e. a digital copy).

Submission Dates and Penalties for Late Submission

The submission of a Master's thesis to the School of Archaeology is a formal process. Any alternative submission date substantially prior to 8 August, 2024 must be first agreed with your thesis supervisor and may require the approval of the Module Coordinator and Graduate Director. The School Office should then be informed of the approved alternative hand-in date. Submission of a thesis by post may be allowed in exceptional circumstances *only if agreed by the School in advance*.

Penalties will apply to any assignments received after the set deadline. Please refer to the [UCD Late Submission of Coursework Policy](#) regarding penalties for late submission.

As per UCD policies, grades and feedback will be returned within 20 working days of thesis submission (i.e. by Thursday, 5 September 2024 on Brightspace for work submitted by the deadline). Provisional results should be released by UCD to students in early October 2024, with final results published in late October (results available via SISWeb). UCD Registry will contact students directly by e-mail with further information on specific dates nearer the time. The School will email students following the publication of final results of the Graduate Taught [Grade Approval Process](#) by UCD Registry in mid-Autumn 2024 with information on the School's informal reception for graduates in early December 2024. Please see the guidelines [Key Dates for UCD Current Students](#) for more details.

Marking

All graduate minor theses are marked by at least two academic staff members. Your supervisor will be the secondary marker. A sample of minor theses will also be sent to our Postgraduate Subject External Examiners for comment. Each Master's thesis will receive a customized rubric for MSc dissertations as well as a brief markers' report (250–500 words) providing initial feedback to each student. This will be uploaded on Brightspace. We encourage those of you seeking further feedback to contact your supervisor directly after the final results are released.

In the case of the MSc in World Heritage Management & Conservation, the Subject External Examiner will visit UCD in September to review the programme including the theses. Students who are available will have the opportunity to meet with the WHMC External

Examiner to discuss their thesis. A meeting by Skype/Zoom/Google Meets may also be possible. It is not absolutely necessary to meet with the Subject External Examiner to complete the programme.

Extenuating Circumstances: Online application

All applications for extenuating circumstances are dealt with online. Further information is detailed in the [UCD Policy on Extenuating Circumstances](#).

If serious or ongoing extenuating circumstances are affecting your engagement with your programme in any semester, you should make an online application via your SISWeb account for Examination Board consideration. Guidelines for how to do so can be found on this page under the tab [How Do I Apply for Extenuating Circumstances?](#)

Research Project Supervisor

Your MSc thesis supervisor will be decided by the School on the basis of research specialization and workload. Supervisors are typically faculty, though postdoctoral researchers or research scientists may supervise a dissertation where research interests align. In these instances, a highly experienced co-supervisor is also assigned. All staff members are highly experienced researchers and will provide you with assistance and guidance throughout the process. A co-supervisor may be assigned to step into the main supervision role if the primary supervisor becomes absent (for example, due to illness or emergency). Decisions about this kind of co-supervision will be made by the Director of Graduate Studies, and the Module Coordinator and/or Head of School, in consultation with programme co-ordinators.

Your MSc thesis supervisor will provide specific guidance for the research you have chosen. As a general rule of thumb you should keep in contact with your supervisor every two to three weeks.

Agreed guidelines by the School of Archaeology for what you should expect from your supervisor are as follows:

- One meeting to confirm the structure of your thesis and your timetable for completion.
- Three further meetings between the first meeting and early-August submission.
- Your supervisor will read and provide feedback on 2–3 chapters, not a full draft.
- The chapters presenting your aims and objectives and your methodology are very important for your supervisor to read so that they can provide feedback and guidance. You should aim to write a draft of these chapters as early as possible during the writing process.
- Supervisors may also read the Discussion and Conclusions, which should reflect your own insights and comments on the significance of the results of your research.
- Some projects may require more contact, advice, or specific training. If you have specific issues that might need addressing, articulate these clearly to your supervisor well in advance so that they have time to consider them and figure out how to best support your research process.
- As the project progresses, you will need feedback from your supervisor on drafts of your work. Your supervisor and other faculty have other professional commitments and responsibilities in addition to supervision; try to give them as much advance notice as possible in terms of when you will submit work and what kind of feedback you need. Remember that just like you, they need to balance work with other aspects of their lives. Treat them as you would want to be treated in their position—you probably wouldn't want a last-minute request to read a 30-page draft and provide feedback in twelve hours, right?

If you have any issues with your supervision or your dissertation progress, in the first instance contact Dr Jess Beck, the MC. If Jess is not able to help you resolve the problem, you can contact your Programme Director. Finally, you may also contact the Graduate Director.

Key Points of Contact

Your key points of contact with the School are your MC, your Supervisor, your Programme Director, the Graduate Director, and the Graduate Taught Student Administrator (Lisa Rogers) in the School Office (masters.archaeology@ucd.ie). The School of Archaeology Office (Room K013) is the administrative hub of the School and should be your first port of call with any questions during your time in the Masters programme

During the Summer Trimester (mid-May–end of August), contact the School Office by e-mailing masters.archaeology@ucd.ie to arrange a meeting with the Graduate Taught Administrator. Please use your UCD Connect e-mail and remember to include your UCD Student number in all e-mails to the School.

Contacting the Module Coordinator

If you have any questions and would like to speak to me, my open office hours during the Spring 2024 Trimester are Wednesday from 11:00 AM–12:00 PM and Thursday from 2:30–3:30 PM. For other times, please email me to arrange an appointment (jess.beck@UCD.ie). You are also welcome to approach me before or after module meetings. Alternatively, I am happy to deal with any queries you may have by email.

MODULE SCHEDULE SPRING 2024

The module runs from 12:00–13:50 every Thursday and meets in the Barry Raftery Seminar Room in Ardmore Annex. Please note that during Week 7, project presentations will take place on Monday, March 4 (11:00 AM–2:00 PM) in Quinn Q-007 and Tuesday, March 5 (9:30 AM–12:00 PM) in Quinn Q-011.

Week	Date	Topic	Assignment
1	Jan 25	Introduction and Research Topics	
2	Feb 1	Research Questions	
3	Feb 8	Bibliography and Literature Review <i>with contributions from Sandra Dunkin (UCD Library)</i>	Abstract, proposed approach, and initial bibliography
4	Feb 15	Methodology and Data Collection <i>with contributions from Dr Steve Davis and Conor McDermott</i>	
5	Feb 22	Project Scope: Proposal SWOT	Proposal SWOT sheet
6	Feb 29	Archaeological Ethics	
7	Mar 4/ Mar 5	Project Presentations	Project presentations
FIELDWORK/STUDY BREAK 11–24 MARCH			
8	Mar 28	Data Analysis and Presentation	
9	April 4	Formatting, Writing, and Time Management	Project proposal
10	April 11	Open Topic and/or Meetings	
11	April 18	Meetings—No Formal Class	
12	April 25	Meetings—No Formal Class	

Note: This is an indicative schedule, and some detail and sequence may change.

READINGS

A full reading list will be posted on Brightspace in advance of our first class meeting.

ASSESSMENT

Only two components of the module assessment are graded: the project proposal, due on 4 April, is worth 5% of your module grade, and the thesis itself, due on 8 August, is worth 95% of your module grade. The remaining assessments are compulsory components of the module for which you will receive qualitative feedback, but this will not directly affect your grade.

Assessment timetable

Description (*=graded)	Due Date	% Final Grade
Project abstract, proposed approach and initial bibliography. <i>This can be submitted as a written assignment (<1500 words plus bibliography) OR as a video assignment (scripted, <10 min, including bibliography)</i>	Thursday, 4 February 2024, by 5:00 PM	0
Project Presentation	Monday, March 4 and Tuesday, March 5	0
*Project Proposal	Thursday, 4 April 2024, by 5:00 PM	5
*Master's minor thesis (digital copy) <i>Please note hard copy is due Thursday, 15 August 2024, by 3:00 PM.</i>	Thursday, 8 August 2024, by 3:00 PM	95

ARCH41390 Readings

Expectations: Core readings should be read in advance of the class meeting for that week. For example, before we meet during Week 2, you should have read the Ackerman (2018) and Booth et al. 2018 chapters, the 2008 encyclopedia entry on research design, and the GMU pamphlet on “how to write a research question. Additional readings provide more details on the topic if you feel you would benefit from a more in-depth overview. Readings are organized in alphabetical order rather than order of importance.

Accessing Readings: Readings with an asterisk (*) are uploaded as pdfs to the module Brightspace in My Learning under the week for which they are assigned. Hyperlinks are provided for all other readings.

Citation Style: This reading list is formatted in Harvard style, which is the reference style you will be using for your master’s thesis. A useful guide to the Harvard Style has been compiled on the UCD library website: <https://libguides.ucd.ie/harvardstyle/introduction>.

Week 1: Introduction and Research Topics (January 25)	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Core (16 pp.)	2
Week 2: Research Questions and Abstracts (February 1)	2
Core (31 pp.)	2
Additional.....	2
Week 3: Bibliography and Literature Review (February 8).....	3
Core (26 pp.)	3
Additional.....	3
Week 4: Methodology and Data Collection (February 15)	4
Core (71 pp+).....	4
Additional.....	4
Week 5: Project Scope and Proposal SWOT (February 22).....	4
Week 6: Archaeological Ethics (February 29)	5
Core (28 pp.)	5
Additional.....	5
Week 7: Project Presentations (March 4, March 7)	5
Week 8: Data Analysis and Presentation (March 28).....	6
Core (19 pp.)	6
Additional.....	6
Week 9: Formatting, Writing, and Time Management (April 4).....	6
Core (54 pp.)	6
Additional.....	7
General References You May Find Useful	7

Week 1: Introduction and Research Topics (January 25)

Core (16 pp.)

*Booth, W. C. et al. 2016. 'From topics to questions', In Booth, W. C. et al. *The craft of research*. 4th edition. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, pp. 33–48.

Week 2: Research Questions and Abstracts (February 1)

Core (31 pp.)

*Ackerman, E. (2018) 'Analyze this' in Graff, G., and Birkenstein, C. (eds.) *They say, I say: The moves that matter in academic writing*. New York: W.W. Norton & Company, pp.224–242.

*Booth, W. C. et al. (2016) 'From questions to a problem', In Booth, W. C. et al. *The craft of research*. 4th edition. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, pp. 49–64.

*Cheek, J. (2008) '[Research design](https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412963909)', in Given, L. M. (ed.) (2008). *The SAGE encyclopedia of qualitative research methods*. SAGE Publications. Available at <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412963909>

George Mason University (2024) How to write a research question. Available at: <https://writingcenter.gmu.edu/writing-resources/research-based-writing>

Additional

*Indiana University Libraries (2024) *Narrowing a topic and developing a research question*. Available at: https://libraries.indiana.edu/sites/default/files/Develop_a_Research_Question.pdf

London School of Economics and Political Science (2024). *How to write an abstract*. Available at: <https://info.lse.ac.uk/current-students/student-futures/how-to-write-an-abstract>

PLoS One (2024) *How to write an abstract*. Available at: <https://plos.org/resource/how-to-write-a-great-abstract/>

*University of Melbourne (2024) *Writing an abstract*. Available at: https://services.unimelb.edu.au/_data/assets/pdf_file/0007/471274/Writing_an_Abstract_Update_051112.pdf

*University of Waterloo (2024) *Develop a research question*. Available at: <https://uwaterloo.ca/writing-and-communication-centre/resources-develop-research-question>

University of Wisconsin-Madison (2024) *Writing an abstract for your research paper*. Available at: <https://writing.wisc.edu/handbook/assignments/writing-an-abstract-for-your-research-paper/>

Week 3: Bibliography and Literature Review (February 8)

Core (26 pp.)

*Graff, G., and Birkenstein, C. (2018) “‘And yet’: Distinguishing what you say from what they say,” in Graff, G., and Birkenstein, C. (eds.) *They say, I say: The moves that matter in academic writing*. New York: W.W. Norton & Company, pp. 67–76.

*Race, R. (2008) ‘[Literature review](https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412963909)’, in Given, L. M. (ed.) (2008). *The SAGE encyclopedia of qualitative research methods*. SAGE Publications. Available at <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412963909>

Ralph, L. (2019) [Twitter] 15 August. Available at: https://twitter.com/laurence_ralph/status/1161826024281260033?lang=en (Accessed 21 January 2024).

*Souleles, D. (2020). ‘What to do with the predator in your bibliography’, *Allegra lab: Anthropology for Radical Optimism*, 15 September. Available at: <https://allegralaboratory.net/what-to-do-with-the-predator-in-your-bibliography/> (Accessed 21 January 2024).

*University of Vermont Graduate Writing Center (2024) ‘An introduction to literature reviews’, Accessed at: [https://www.uvm.edu/sites/default/files/Graduate-Writing-Center/GWC%20Guides/Genres/An Introduction to Literature Reviews.pdf](https://www.uvm.edu/sites/default/files/Graduate-Writing-Center/GWC%20Guides/Genres/An%20Introduction%20to%20Literature%20Reviews.pdf) (Accessed 21 January 2024).

Additional

Cite Black Women (2024) Available at: <https://www.citeblackwomenscollective.org/>

*Smith, C. A., & Garrett-Scott, D. (2021) ‘We are not named’: Black women and the politics of citation in anthropology’, *Feminist Anthropology*, 2(1), 18–37. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/fea2.12038>

*Tushingam, S., Fulkerson, T. & Hill, K. (2017) ‘The peer review gap: a longitudinal case study of gendered publishing and occupational patterns in a female-rich discipline, Western North America (1974–2016)’, *PLoS ONE*, 12(11), e0188403. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0188403>.

Week 4: Methodology and Data Collection (February 15)

Core (71 pp+)

Note: This may seem like a metric ton of reading, but Fogelin is engaging, snappy, and funny. His pages are large-print and his writing easy to speed through. Aside from the Fogelin, I ask you to read *either* the quantitative chapter or the qualitative chapter from the Pearson textbook, depending on what you are most interested in. You may, of course, read both if you are interested or a masochist.

*Fogelin, L. (2019) 'Learning to love lousy data', In *An unauthorized companion to American archaeological theory*, EPUB, pp. 33–62.

*Plano Clark, V.L, Creswell, J W. (2021) 'Quantitative research designs: recognizing the overall plan for a study', In *Understanding research: a consumer's guide*, 2nd edn. Boston, Pearson, pp. TBD.

*Plano Clark, V.L, Creswell, J W. (2021) 'Qualitative research designs: recognizing the overall plan for a study', In *Understanding research: a consumer's guide*, 2nd edn. Boston, Pearson, pp.TBD.

*Schensul, J. J. (2008b) '[Methods](https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412963909)', in Given, L. M. (ed.) (2008). *The SAGE encyclopedia of qualitative research methods*. SAGE Publications. Available at <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412963909>

Additional

*Binford, L.R. (1964) 'A consideration of archaeological research design', *American Antiquity* 29(4): 425–440.

*Fogelin, L. (2019) 'Preface', In *An unauthorized companion to American archaeological theory*, EPUB, pp. xii–xx.

*Fogelin, L. (2019) 'Theory is not Excalibur', In *An unauthorized companion to American archaeological theory*, EPUB, pp. 22-35.

*Schensul, J. J. (2008a) '[Methodology](https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412963909)', in Given, L. M. (ed.) (2008). *The SAGE encyclopedia of qualitative research methods*. SAGE Publications. Available at <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412963909>

Week 5: Project Scope and Proposal SWOT (February 22)

No readings—proposal SWOT.

Week 6: Archaeological Ethics (February 29)

Core (28 pp.)

*Plummer Sires, J. (2021). 'Black Lives Matter and museums in 2020: a personal and professional perspective.' *American Anthropologist*, 123(4), pp.957–959. Available at <https://doi.org/10.1111/aman13668>. (Accessed 21 January 2024).

*Smith, R. W. A, and Bolnick, D. A. (2019) Situating science: doing biological anthropology as a view from somewhere. *American Anthropologist*, 121(2): pp. 465–466. Available at <https://doi.org/10.1111/aman.13213>. (Accessed 21 January 2024).

*Society for American Archaeology (2024) *Principles of archaeological ethics*. Available at: <https://www.saa.org/career-practice/ethics-in-professional-archaeology>

*University College Dublin (2024) *Code of good practice in research*. Available at: <https://www.ucd.ie/researchethics/t4media/UCD%20REC%20Code%20of%20Good%20Practice%20in%20Research%20%20December%202019.pdf>

*University College Dublin (2024) *Research ethics UCD policy*. Available at: <https://www.ucd.ie/researchethics/t4media/Policy%20on%20Research%20Ethics%202018.pdf>

Additional

Beisaw, A. M., et al. (eds.) (2023). 'Sins of our ancestors (and of ourselves): confronting archaeological legacies.' *Archaeological Papers of the American Anthropological Association*, 34. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/apaa.12153>. (Accessed 21 January 2024)

Note: This collection of 12 articles offers a comprehensive look at ethical issues faced by archaeologists today. While the focus is on American archaeology, the ethical questions posed by the issue are global in scope. [The entire volume can be accessed through the UCD library.](#)

*Hicks, D. (2021) 'Decolonising museums isn't part of a 'culture war'. It's about keeping them relevant.' *The Guardian*, 7 May. Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/commentisfree/2021/may/07/decolonising-museums-isnt-part-of-a-culture-war-its-about-keeping-them-relevant>.

*Joyce, R. A. (2021) 'Science, objectivity, and academic freedom in the twenty-first century,' *International Journal of Cultural Property*, 28(2), pp. 193–199. Available at <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0940739121000230>. (Accessed 21 January 2024).

*Overholtzer, L., and Argueta, J. R. (2017) 'Letting skeletons out of the closet: the ethics of displaying ancient Mexican human remains,' *International Journal of Heritage Studies*, 24(5), pp. 508–530. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13527258.2017.1390486> (accessed 21 January 2024).

Week 7: Project Presentations (March 4, March 7)

No readings—project presentations.

Week 8: Data Analysis and Presentation (March 28)

Core (19 pp.)

*Davis, C. S. (2008) '[Hypothesis](https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412963909)', in Given, L. M. (ed.) (2008). *The SAGE encyclopedia of qualitative research methods*. SAGE Publications. Available at <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412963909>

*Huff, D. (1993) 'The gee-whiz graph', *How to lie with statistics*, New York, Norton, pp.60–65.

*Morgan, D. L. (2008) '[Sample](https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412963909)', in Given, L. M. (ed.) (2008). *The SAGE encyclopedia of qualitative research methods*. SAGE Publications. Available at <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412963909>

*Schreiber, J. B. (2008) '[Data](https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412963909)', in Given, L. M. (ed.) (2008). *The SAGE encyclopedia of qualitative research methods*. SAGE Publications. Available at <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412963909>

*Schreiber, J. B. (2008) '[Descriptive statistics](https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412963909)', in Given, L. M. (ed.) (2008). *The SAGE encyclopedia of qualitative research methods*. SAGE Publications. Available at <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412963909>

*Schreiber, J. B. (2008) '[Statistics](https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412963909)', in Given, L. M. (ed.) (2008). *The SAGE encyclopedia of qualitative research methods*. SAGE Publications. Available at <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412963909>

Additional

*Huff, D. (1993) 'Post-hoc rides again', *How to lie with statistics*, New York, Norton, pp. 87–99.

*Huff, D. (1993) 'How to statisticulate', *How to lie with statistics*, New York, Norton, pp.100–121.

Week 9: Formatting, Writing, and Time Management (April 4)

Core (54 pp.)

*Belcher, W. L. (2009) 'Week 1: Designing your plan for writing', In *Writing your journal article in 12 weeks: a guide to academic publishing success*, Los Angeles, Sage, pp. 1–41.

NOTE: Though I have provided the entire chapter, all you need to read is pp. 1–10 and 18–41!

*Lamott, A. (2005) 'Shitty first drafts', In Eschholz, P., Rosa, A., and Clark, V., *Language awareness: readings for college writers*, 9 edn. Boston, Bedford/St. Martin's, pp.93–96.

*Silvia, P. (2019) 'Specious barriers to writing a lot' In *How to write a lot: a practical guide to productive academic writing*, 2nd edn. Washington D.C., American Psychological Association, pp.11–27.

Before you come to class, please also skim the following. A printed copy will be provided for you in class:

*Graff, G., and Birkenstein, C. (2006) 'Templates,' In Graff, G., and Birkenstein, C., (eds.), *They say/ I say: the moves that matter in academic writing*, New York, Norton.

Additional

*Bizup, J., and Williams, J. M. (2014) 'Global coherence' In, Bizup, J., and Williams, J. M., *Style: lessons in clarity and grace*, 11th edn. Essex, Pearson, pp. 125–137.

*Bizup, J., and Williams, J. M. (2014) 'Shape' In, Bizup, J., and Williams, J. M., *Style: lessons in clarity and grace*, 11th edn. Pearson, Essex, pp. 157–182.

*Lamott, A. (2-2-) 'On perfectionism', In *Bird by bird: some instructions on writing and life*. Edinburgh, Canongate, pp. 57–61.

*Silvia, P. (2019) 'The care and feeding of writing schedules', In *How to write a lot: a practical guide to productive academic writing*, 2nd edn. Washington D.C., American Psychological Association, pp.29–46.

*University of Vermont Graduate Writing Center. (2024). 'Tips from Paul Silvia's *How to Write a Lot: A Practical Guide to Academic Writing*'. Available at:

https://www.uvm.edu/sites/default/files/Graduate-Writing-Center/GWC%20Guides/Habits/Writing_Productivity_Tips.pdf (Accessed 21 January 2024)

General References You May Find Useful

These books provide useful general references for academic writing, productivity, and research design. I've read many of these books myself over the last few years while seeking to refine my own approaches to writing and time management. To compile this list, I've also solicited advice from colleagues who have taught university writing classes or similar research design modules at other institutions. Where possible, I have linked to the UCD library page to make it easier for you to find these resources, and noted when specific volumes are available as e-books. Happy reading!

Belcher, W. (2019) [Writing your journal article in twelve weeks: a guide to academic publishing success](#), 2nd edn. Chicago, University of Chicago Press.

This book is particularly useful for anyone considering publishing their thesis after achieving their MSc. Belcher's tips on writing practice are thoughtful and accessible, and she provides many writing accountability templates and useful advice on structuring your time.

Booth, W. C. et al. (2016). [The craft of research](#), 4th edn. Chicago, University of Chicago Press.

This volume provides a structured guide to thinking through the steps of research design and project structure. We are already be reading several chapters of the book over the course of the module, but the entire book is available as an e-book in the UCD library should you wish to peruse it further.

Fogelin, L. (2019). *An unauthorized companion to American archaeological theory*. Available at https://www.academia.edu/40368858/An_Unauthorized_Companion_to_American_Archaeological_Theory_EPUB (Accessed 24 January 2024).

This book is a fantastic, fast-paced introduction to archaeological theory. It is intended to be read in tandem with an archaeological theory course, and in recommending it here I assume that you are getting a heavy dose of theory in your other master's-level modules. We are reading the preface and first two chapters as part of this module, but the rest of the book covers various theoretical approaches in more detail. Fogelin has also VERY HELPFULLY prepared initial reading lists on core

bodies of theory, ranging from agency to embodiment to queer archaeology. I highly recommend skimming through these lists to see what might be useful for your own project and research interests. The other great thing about this volume is that it is free to download as both an [E-PUB](#) and a [pdf](#), as part of a laudable experiment in open-access publishing that Fogelin has reflected upon in the [Society for American Archaeology Archaeological Record](#).

Given, L. M. (ed.) (2008). [The SAGE encyclopedia of qualitative research methods](#). SAGE Publications. Available at <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412963909>

This encyclopedia provides concise and clear definitions of key building blocks of qualitative research design. Even if you are leaning towards a quantitative project, I recommend taking ten minutes to skim through the entries to see if there is anything pertinent to your work.

Graff, G., and Birkenstein, C. (2006) [“They say, I say”: the moves that matter in academic writing](#), 4th edn. London, W.W. Norton.

The “template” that we cover during Week 9 is a useful reference for all academics, regardless of career stage. This whole book may be helpful for those of you looking to strengthen your skills in academic writing and argumentation.

Newport, C. (2016) [Deep work: rules for focused success in a distracted world](#), London, Piatkus.

I read this book when searching for strategies to improve my own work-life balance. Newport is an Associate Professor of Computer Science at Georgetown University in the USA, so comes at issues of focus with an understanding of academic workloads and mindsets. The book doesn’t critically engage with cultural and historical understandings of productivity or academic value, but it does provide a useful framework for interrogating your own work structures and practices.

Silvia, P. (2018). [How to write a lot: a practical guide to productive academic writing](#), 2nd edn. Washington D.C., American Psychological Association.

This is another book I read while thinking through my own writing practices. [Silvia](#) is another academic—a Professor of Psychology at the University of North Carolina, Greensboro, and so is well-positioned to provide a useful perspective on academic writing. I found this a quick, snappy, engaging read. If you benefit from co-working and collective strategies for ensuring accountability, one chapter you may find of particular interest is his guide to starting a writing group (Chapter 4).

Strunk, W., and White, E.B. (1979). [The elements of style](#), 3rd edn. New York, MacMillan Publishing.

The quintessential old school guide to strong, clear writing. Should you need a more illustrious recommendation, it’s on Stephen King’s list of resources for writers who want to improve their craft. You can find cheap used copies online or at many second-hand bookstores.

The University of Vermont Graduate Writing Center
<https://www.uvm.edu/gradwriting/writing-resources>

This website contains many excellent writing resources for post graduate level academic writing, including supports for brainstorming and drafting, revising and editing, academic and professional genres, and cultivating productive, healthy writing habits. We have used some of their handouts in this module already, but I recommend exploring what is available on the website as well.